

THE BIBLICAL WORLDVIEW

HOW PENTECOSTAL CHRISTIANS ARE OVERTURNING ISLAMISATION - A CASE STUDY OF NIGERIA

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Islamisation has been defined as a process whereby a society [and even entire countries in this context] convert to the religion of Islam, encompassing the adoption of Islamic practices, values, or institutions [1] [2] [3].

The process of Islamisation is a slow process generally using coercion or pressure bending society to the will of the Islamists [whose main goal it is to take over the world and establish Sharia law on all persons regardless of religious beliefs]. Take for example, the nation of Turkey where Christians comprised between 20 to 25% of the population around 1914 and falling sharply from there to about 2% by 1927 and to 0.2 - 0.5% by today [this decline was largely caused due to the 1913-1923 genocide against Christians where around 3 Million Armenian, Greek and Assyrian Christians, who made up nearly 20% of Turkey's population of 15 Million people were genocided by the Islamist government of Turkey [4] and the rest being forcibly converted to Islam].

These changes that I have mentioned above, have taken place in not just the country that I have cited above as an example, but also in multiple other countries in Middle East and North Africa such as Egypt, Algeria, Libya and Tunisia that were once Christian majority countries for close to at least half a millennium. [5] [6] [6(a)] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12]

However, this article for all purposes and intents shall focus on how de-islamisation has been taking place in the nation of Nigeria [which is poised to become the largest economy in Africa and have one of the largest populations in the world by the year 2075] over the course of the last 36 years. It must also be noted that the nation of Nigeria is also called as the eagle of Africa as it is one of the very few countries in Africa with an economy that has crossed the \$300 Billion GDP mark as of 2025 [13]. Moreover, Nigeria also holds the 12th largest petroleum and oil reserves, with the Nigerian population also making leaps and bounds through their contribution to the Nigerian service sector. Nigeria also has one of the largest militaries in all of Africa with an army that stands strong at 230,000 active personnel.

RELIGIOUS BACKGROUND OF NIGERIA :

The story of Islam in Nigeria begins in the 11th century where Islam arrived to the tribes of Nigeria through the trans Saharan trade routes with the northern parts of Nigeria, being incorporated into the Kanem Empire later called as Kanem Bornu which comprises of the present day Borno state and parts of Chad [14] [15]. This further grew during the 14th century, where under the patronage of the Mali empire during Mansa Musa's reign, the Islamic Wangara traders introduced Islam to the north western, South and South Western parts of Nigeria [16].

However, the actual process of Islamification of Nigeria began in earnest in the year 1804 under the so-called Sheikh Usman Dan Fodio who declared a holy war [also called as Jihad] on Nigeria with the help of his fellow Islamic Fulani clansmen [17]. Most of the states dominated by the Hausa tribe were completely conquered by the year 1808 during the said Jihad under Usman Dan Fodio, who then declared the start of a new Caliphate which is now known as the Sokoto caliphate as its capital was based in the city of Sokoto with the Sultan of Sokoto, being known as the Caliph [or rather as Amir Ul Mu'minin which means commander of the faithful in Arabic] [18]. Under the rule of the Sokoto caliphate, most of northern Nigeria and the middle belt in Nigeria was conquered and incorporated into the caliphate, thus bringing close to 70 to 80% of the [modern day] Nigerian territory under the rule of the Islamic Sultan of Sokoto [19]. Almost all people living in the territory were then converted to Islam ruthlessly by the Khalifa. It is thus estimated that by the year 1913, when the caliphate was abolished by the British who had conquered Nigeria, the estimated Muslim population of the caliphate stood at 65-90% of the total population of this territory [20].

However, with the British came the advent of Christianity into Nigeria, where both catholic and protestant missionaries worked in earnest to convert Nigerians to the Christian faith. However, following the independence of Nigeria from Great Britain, the work of the missionaries slowed down as they were no longer protected by the British but rather had to take the risk to evangelise in Nigeria. Yet, despite these initial setbacks, Christianity did grow steadily in Nigeria from approximately 21.4% of the population in 1953 [see page 55 of the following report : <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/wp-content/uploads/sites/7/2011/12/Christianity-fullreport-web.pdf>] to nearly 35% of the population of the country by the time of the Nigerian Civil War [21] [21(a)].

However, the actual boom in Christianity in Nigeria was accelerated by the arrival and the work of various Pentecostal evangelists such as Benny Hinn, Benson Idahosa, T.B Joshua, William Kumuyi, E. A. Adeboye etc. to Nigeria who began evangelisation of the masses in all areas of Nigeria leading to mass conversions of Muslims and Animists alike to Christianity. This period was also marked by the arrival of the crusade evangelism of Reinhard Bonnke to Nigeria in 1999 to 2017, which led to tens of millions of people converting to [Pentecostal] Christianity in the said time period [22] [22(a)] [23] [23(a)].

REINHARD BONNKE AND THE ERA OF MASS CRUSADE EVANGELISATION -

Beginning in the 1990's and the early 2000's, Pentecostal and Charismatic Christians began holding mass gospel crusades and evangelisation campaigns leading to exponential growth of pentecostal and charismatic churches and also the setting up of many mega churches in south Nigeria and the middle belt of Nigeria.

However, the crusades of Reinhard Bonnke held in the early 2000's and the late 1990's saw a massive number of converts to pentecostal and charismatic christianity, with some sources estimating nearly 55-60 Million Nigerians converting to pentecostal and charismatic christianity within this time frame [24].

Full Video can be found at : [Evangelism in Nigeria - Reinhard Bonnke](#)

Moreover, the early success of CFAN in Nigeria led to an increasing number of Pentecostal and Charismatic pastors holding their own crusades in Nigeria and opening their own ministries and mega churches in various parts of this nation.

Full Video can be found at : [Holy Spirit Outpouring upon Youth in Nigeria - Andres Bisonni Ministries](#)

These crusades and prayer movements started by the Pentecostal and Charismatic Christian community in Nigeria led to an exponential growth in a number of believing Pentecostal and Charismatic Christians, which again led to an exploding number of churches and house church movements being established all across Nigeria. This inevitably led to a large portion of the Southern and the middle belt of Nigeria, converting to Christianity [largely to pentecostalism, and charismatic Christianity]. As the core tenets of pentecostalism and Charismatic Christianity are based on the Great Commission given by the Lord Jesus Christ to his disciples to "preach the gospel to all flesh and make disciples of all nations" as recorded in Matthew 28:19 & Mark 16:15, these sub-sects of Christianity are known for rapidly producing evangelists from within their churches with a zeal to preach about Jesus and the tenets of Christianity as defined by the gospel and thus make converts or disciples of many, in fact even new converts to the Pentecostal and Charismatic movements have begun evangelisation within the first few years of their conversions as noted by the Chinese Charismatic Christian missionary called Brother Yun in his book titled "The Heavenly Man : the remarkable true story of Chinese Christian Brother Yun" [25], thus causing an explosive expansion of the Pentecostal and Charismatic movement over time in whichever country it has established a rooted presence.

It is therefore due to this nature of the Pentecostal and Charismatic church movement that it has already begun expanding into the entirety of North Nigeria, with entire tribes and villages converting to Christianity from Islam furthering the religious divide within Nigeria, caused due to the rapid expansion of the aggressively evangelistic form of Christianity that is found in Pentecostalism and Charismatic Christianity.

DATA AND STATISTICS ON CONVERSIONS OF MUSLIMS TO CHRISTIANITY

While various statistics place the number of Muslims who have converted to Christianity in Nigeria at close to 1 Million people, it has to be said that these statistics do not paint the full picture of the rate at which muslims are apostatising to Pentecostal and Charismatic Christianity. This can be proven by the recent journal article titled "The Muslim response to the Pentecostal surge in Nigeria : Prayer and the rise of Charismatic Islam" published on taylor and francis online [26] which states that due to the growth of Pentecostal and Charismatic Christianity in Nigeria, it has caused wide-spread hemorrhaging of young muslim men and women to Pentecostal Christian groups [27], forcing mosques and muslim imams to adapt to a more pentecostalised and charismatic form of Islam to prevent this mass apostasy.

In effect, what I call "Charismatic Islam" ensues as a by-product of four intermixing currents: inter-faith competition for power; Christian conversionary impulse; independent internal discourses and tensions among Muslim intellectuals; and a variety of institutional and individual transnational agents who have played a key role in the forging of Muslim identity in Nigeria. Arguably the most visible symbol of Islamic revivalism is the phenomenon of Muslim youth prayer movements, many of which, presumably, have been established to provide the kind of organizational equivalent that would stop the hemorrhaging of young Muslim men and women to Pentecostal groups. Such organizations have drawn on the nous and organizational savvy of "literate and upwardly mobile Muslim professionals and businessmen; many of whom could not be accommodated by any of the existing Muslim organizations like the MSS, YOUMBAS,⁸ etc - which, in any case, were not equipped to solve the problems of life cycle, (mis)fortune in business, or the destructive machinations of the (sic) evil forces - issues that new generation Christian churches, titans of the new power-for-prosperity market, were providing their patrons and clientele" (Sanni 2012: 160).

Link to the said article and citation : [Nigeria : Prayer and the rise of Charismatic Islam](#)

However, while the above article admits that Pentecostal and Charismatic groups are converting Muslims en masse to Pentecostal and charismatic Christianity [denoted and implied by the phrase "hemorrhaging of young muslim men and women to Pentecostal groups"; where the word hemorrhage literally means "to lose a large amount of blood in a short time" as given in the Cambridge dictionary [28] or "to lose rapidly and uncontrollably" as given in the Merriam-Webster dictionary [29], it still does not give us precise figures on how many muslims are estimated to have converted to Christianity, especially Pentecostal and Charismatic Christianity [in light of the above journal article].

Therefore, in order to draw up rough estimates, we shall study data from 3 main sources namely : pre-2020 religious population estimates; the 2020, 2022 and 2025 surveys conducted by the Afro-barometer and finally a comparative analysis of the Pew research survey on the Israeli - Gaza war [of 2023 - 2025].

PRE 2020 SURVEYS :

There are several surveys and estimates drawn by various Organisations such as the CIA [from the CIA factbook] and Pew Research etc.

Pew Research statistics [as of 2019] place the Christian population of Nigeria at roughly 48.1% of the total population of the country while it places the Muslim population of Nigeria at roughly 50% of the total population [30].

10 countries with the largest Muslim populations, 2015 and 2060

2015	2015 MUSLIM POPULATION	% OF COUNTRY THAT IS MUSLIM	% OF WORLD'S MUSLIM POPULATION IN 2015	2060	2060 MUSLIM POPULATION	% OF COUNTRY PROJECTED TO BE MUSLIM	% OF WORLD'S MUSLIM POPULATION IN 2060
1 Indonesia	219,980,000	87.1%	12.6%	1 India	333,090,000	19.4%	11.1%
2 India	194,810,000	14.9	11.1	2 Pakistan	283,650,000	96.5	9.5
3 Pakistan	184,000,000	96.4	10.5	3 Nigeria	283,160,000	60.5	9.5
4 Bangladesh	144,020,000	90.6	8.2	4 Indonesia	253,450,000	86.1	8.5
5 Nigeria	90,020,000	50.0	5.1	5 Bangladesh	181,800,000	91.9	6.1
6 Egypt	83,870,000	95.1	4.8	6 Egypt	124,380,000	96.6	4.2
7 Iran	77,650,000	99.5	4.4	7 Iraq	94,000,000	99.3	3.1
8 Turkey	75,460,000	98.0	4.3	8 Turkey	88,410,000	97.9	3.0
9 Algeria	37,210,000	97.9	2.1	9 Iran	82,980,000	99.7	2.8
10 Iraq	36,200,000	99.0	2.1	10 Afghanistan	81,870,000	99.7	2.7
Subtotal	1,143,200,000		65.2	Subtotal	1,806,790,000		60.5
Subtotal for rest of world	609,420,000		34.8	Subtotal for rest of world	1,180,600,000		39.5
World total	1,752,620,000		100.0	World total	2,987,390,000		100.0

Source: The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections, 2010-2050.
Population estimates are rounded to the nearest 10,000. Percentages are calculated from unrounded numbers.

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10 countries with the largest Christian populations, 2015 and 2060

2015	2015 CHRISTIAN POPULATION	% OF COUNTRY THAT IS CHRISTIAN	% OF WORLD'S CHRISTIAN POPULATION IN 2015	2060	2060 CHRISTIAN POPULATION	% OF COUNTRY PROJECTED TO BE CHRISTIAN	% OF WORLD'S CHRISTIAN POPULATION IN 2060
1 U.S.	248,180,000	76.9%	10.9%	1 U.S.	262,330,000	63.9%	8.6%
2 Brazil	179,910,000	88.5	7.9	2 Brazil	186,550,000	86.0	6.1
3 Mexico	113,620,000	94.6	5.0	3 Nigeria	174,270,000	37.2	5.7
4 Russia	103,490,000	73.1	4.5	4 D.R. Congo	160,070,000	95.7	5.2
5 Philippines	94,300,000	92.5	4.1	5 Philippines	152,320,000	91.9	5.0
6 Nigeria	86,650,000	48.1	3.8	6 Mexico	127,790,000	90.6	4.2
7 D.R. Congo	72,090,000	95.9	3.2	7 Tanzania	117,930,000	67.4	3.9
8 China	70,890,000	5.2	3.1	8 Uganda	96,200,000	83.8	3.1
9 Ethiopia	57,450,000	62.4	2.5	9 Kenya	91,780,000	81.4	3.0
10 Germany	54,880,000	67.3	2.4	10 Ethiopia	87,660,000	57.1	2.9
Subtotal	1,081,460,000		47.5	Subtotal	1,456,900,000		47.7
Subtotal for rest of world	1,194,790,000		52.5	Subtotal for rest of world	1,597,560,000		52.3
World total	2,276,250,000		100.0	World total	3,054,460,000		100.0

Source: The Future of World Religions: Population Growth Projections, 2010-2050.
Population estimates are rounded to the nearest 10,000. Percentages are calculated from unrounded numbers.

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For the entire table refer to the following Link : [The countries with the 10 largest Christian populations and the 10 largest Muslim populations](https://thebiblicalworldview123.blogspot.com/2026/03/how-pentecostal-christians-are.html)

However, the CIA factbook placed estimates of the Muslim population at roughly 53.5% and the Christian population at roughly 45.9% of the total population as of 2018 [31].

Why the statistics given above are wrong :

It must be noted that the previous figures and statistics are by and large estimates given by PEW research organisation, and even the CIA. These estimates are not based on any actual survey or any recent census taken in the country of Nigeria. This explains why the estimates given by pew research organisation keep varying every few year i.e. the 2020 report by pew research places muslims at 56% of the total population and the Christians at just 43% of the total population [32] [32(a)], which is an impossibility, considering that their own report just the previous year, placed the Christian population at 48% of the total population [33] and the Muslim population at 50% of the total population [34]. Therefore if their 2019 and 2020 are both true then this would roughly mean that 6% of all Christians, which is equivalent to nearly 14 Million Individuals converted to Islam in just one year, an event that would have sent shockwaves throughout Nigeria and the rest of Africa and the world if it was possible and did take place.

Secondly, the PEW Research report of 2020 and 2025 which places the Muslim population of Nigeria at roughly 56% of the total population has not been based on any direct survey conducted by the PEW Research organisation itself, but rather they have reported to rely on the survey conducted by the DHS Program in Nigeria on the basis of the survey conducted by the DHS of roughly 39,050 individuals [35] [35(a)]. However, the problem with the said survey of the DHS is that it severely under-represents or disproportionately surveys entire groups of people within Nigeria on the basis of the region that they live in. For Example : The DHS report states that roughly 32% of those surveyed in this report belong to the north western parts of Nigeria [as given in the second paragraph on page 84 of the following [PDF](#) and page 40 of the following report : <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR395/FR395.pdf>] and roughly 8% of those who were surveyed were from South East Nigeria, which is clearly a case of disproportionate representation because, in reality roughly 25-28%[36] of the total population of Nigeria [37] lives in North West Nigeria [which is predominantly muslim], while 11-12% of the total Nigerian population lives in South East Nigeria [38]. Thereby, by the very own admission of the survey report [as given page 84 of the online PDF report] the muslims belonging to North-west Nigeria have been over represented by roughly 4 to 7 percentage points [relative to the actual total population of Nigeria], Whereas the Christians of Southeast Nigeria have been under represented by 3 to 4 percentage points [relative to the actual total population of Nigeria] in the said survey.

Thirdly, this survey has also over-represented the Hausa Ethnic group within Nigeria who make up 33%-34% of all respondents and it has under-represented the Yoruba and Igbo ethnic groups who make up 13% and 11% of all respondents in this survey respectively. This is problematic for the following reasons, namely :

- 1) Hausa's are largely Muslim, with a large majority of Hausa's practicing Islam for generations. However, they only make up 25% of the population of Nigeria [39] at the very least or 30% at the very most [40]. Therefore, by having roughly 33% of respondents as Hausa's it shows that Hausa muslims were by and large over-represented in the said survey.
- 2) Yoruba's are by and large Christian with a small minority of the Yoruba's practising Islam; Moreover, Yoruba's make up 21% [41] of Nigeria's entire population [42]. Therefore, having only 13% of all respondents as Yoruba severely under-represents the Yoruba Christians among the respondents of the survey proportionate to the various muslim tribes in Nigeria.
- 3) Igbo's are almost entirely christian, with an absolute minority of Igbo's practising Islam [if any]. Moreover, Igbo's also make up roughly between 18% - 21% of the total population of Nigeria [43]. Thereby, making it crystal clear that Igbo Christians were severely under-represented by almost as much as 10 percentage points in proportion to their own actual population and as much as 52.4% percentage points relative to the Hausa Muslims.

Therefore, these above grounds are clear enough to show us that the DHS survey has no concrete proof or evidence of being reliable enough to be cited as the actual statistics on the religion or faith followed by Nigerians, inside the country.

This clearly shows us the need for an actual survey or census based report that can actually show us ground realities and estimates on the religious [christian and muslim] population within Nigeria.

THE AFRO-BAROMETER SURVEYS :

We shall begin by looking at three surveys taken in 2024 [44] [44(a)] [45] [45(a)], 2022 [46] [46(a)] [47] [47(a)] and 2020 [48] [48(a)] by the organisation known as Afro barometer, which surveyed roughly 1600 different individuals for each of these surveys from all over Nigeria aged 18 and older, in face to face interviews during their fieldwork to arrive at their estimates, and they self report a margin of error about ± 2.5 percentage points and 95% confidence levels in their reporting.

Ogun	3.5	3.2
Ondo	2.5	2.7
Osun	2.0	2.3
Oyo	4.0	3.9
Plateau	2.0	2.2
Rivers	4.0	3.9
Sokoto	2.5	2.3
Taraba	1.5	1.6
Yobe	1.5	1.5
Zamfara	2.5	2.4
Education		
No formal education	16.9	15.9
Primary	18.3	18.2
Secondary	38.5	38.6
Post-secondary	28.4	27.8
Don't know	0.1	
Religion		
Christian	59.9	51.4
Muslim	46.3	47.7
Other	0.6	0.7
Don't know	0.2	0.1

Q1. How old are you?

	Urban	Rural	Men	Women	Total
18-25 years	24.3	29.2	24.2	30.3	27.1
26-35 years	30.0	29.7	25.8	33.9	29.8
36-45 years	26.7	22.6	27.2	21.4	24.4
46-55 years	11.7	10.4	12.0	9.9	11.0
56-65 years	5.4	6.1	7.3	4.2	5.8
Over 65 years	1.9	2.0	3.5	0.3	1.9

Q2. What is the primary language you speak in your home now?

	Urban	Rural	Men	Women	Total
English	9.9	9.9	5.7	4.1	5.9
Hausa	24.3	38.8	35.4	34.4	32.5
Igbo	1.7	7.2	12.6	10.1	11.4
Yoruba	28.9	10	17.2	17.3	17.3
Pidgin English	1.6	1.4	1.6	1.4	1.5
Efik	1	2.8	1.9	2.2	2
Ebira	0.8	0	0.2	0.5	0.3
Fulani	2.2	2.4	2.6	2	2.3
Itoko	0.2	1.7	1	1.2	1.1
Kanuri	0	1.3	0.8	0.7	0.8
Tiv	1.2	3.7	2.8	2.4	2.6
Nupe	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.4
Ijaw	0.7	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.2
Edo	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.2
Igala	0.2	1.1	0.6	0.7	0.7
Urhobo	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.3
Anang	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6
Idoma	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7
Ison	0.2	0	0.1	0.1	0.1
Babur	0.4	1.1	0.9	0.7	0.8

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For the entire table and result of the 2024 afrobarometer survey refer to page 6 the following Link : [SUMMARY OF RESULTS : Afrobarometer Round 10 survey in Nigeria, 2024](#)

Ondo	2.5	2.7
Osun	2.5	2.4
Oyo	4.0	4.0
Plateau	2.0	2.2
Rivers	4.0	4.1
Sokoto	2.5	2.4
Taraba	1.5	1.3
Yobe	1.5	1.6
Zamfara	2.0	2.2
Education		
No formal education	17.3	15.8
Primary	17.1	17.7
Secondary	49.9	43.3
Post-secondary	29.7	23.1
Refused	0.1	0.1
Religion		
Christian	50.1	54.2
Muslim	46.5	45.5
Other	0.3	0.2
Don't know	0.1	0.1

Q1. How old are you?

	Urban	Rural	Men	Women	Total
18-25	26.0	30.5	24.0	33.1	29.4
26-35	31.3	30.7	29.3	32.7	31.0
36-45	22.2	19.2	21.7	19.1	20.5
46-55	9.4	10.9	12.1	8.2	10.2
56-65	6.5	6.4	7.4	5.4	6.4
Over 65	2.4	2.4	3.5	1.6	2.5

Q2. What is the primary language you speak in your home?

	Urban	Rural	Men	Women	Total
English	9.8	5.2	6.4	8.0	7.2
Hausa	24.5	36.8	32.1	31.0	31.5
Igbo	16.7	10.1	12.2	13.7	12.9
Yoruba	28.5	8.7	17.7	16.7	17.2
Pidgin English	1.6	1.5	1.8	1.3	1.6
Efik	0.5	2.4	1.2	1.9	1.6
Ebira	0.2			0.1	0.1
Fulani	0.5	2.1	1.7	1.2	1.4
Itoko	0.1		0.1		0.1
Itoko	0.7	2.6	1.6	2.0	1.8
Kanuri	0.4			0.4	0.2
Tiv	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3
Nupe	0.7	1.3	0.9	1.2	1.0
Ijaw	1.5	0.7	0.8	1.3	1.0
Edo	1.3		0.8	0.3	0.6
Igala	0.3	1.8	1.2	1.1	1.2
Urhobo	2.9	0.4	1.6	1.3	1.5
Ogoni		0.1		0.1	0.1

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For the entire table and result of the 2022 afrobarometer survey refer to page 6 the following Link : [SUMMARY OF RESULTS : Afrobarometer Round 9 survey in Nigeria, 2022](#)

Figure 2: Religious affiliation | by country | 34 countries | 2016/2018

Respondents were asked: What is your religion, if any?

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For the entire table and result of the 2020 afrobarometer survey refer to page 4 the following Link : [Afrobarometer Dispatch No. 339 | Brian Howard | 28 January 2020](#)

Now, a close look at the results of the Afro-barometer survey held in Nigeria from the year 2020-2025 places the Christian population of Nigeria at a clear majority of the total population of Nigeria i.e. between 52% [lower bound as per 2024 survey] and 56% [higher bound as per the 2020 survey] of the total population of Nigeria. Considering that, for each of these surveys more than 1600 people were personally interviewed on site and face-to-face over a period of three different years and three different times i.e. 2020, 2022 and 2024, bringing the total number of people surveyed over these 3 different years at 4800 individuals; Therefore it shows that the data collected has a very small margin of error and is uniform as there has been minimal and minute difference between the data shown over the five years [which would not be the case if the surveys were biased or ununiformly and heavily concentrated in just one region of Nigeria].

Secondly, the organisation that has done the job of surveying these 1600 people, have attested to the fact that in each of these surveys, the confidence level of the survey stands at 95% with a margin of error at just 2.5% [give or take] as reported earlier. Thus assuming that 2.5% of the surveyed population marked their religious beliefs incorrectly, it would still give us a report showing nearly 50% of the population of Nigeria as Christians [as the lower bound figure] and nearly 54% of the population of Nigeria as Christians [as the higher bound figure].

However, even with this report which clearly shows that Christians have now become a clear majority of Nigeria's population any critic would be inclined to say that these surveys

or reports could be biased towards Christianity or they do not take into account the Northern states of Nigeria which holds a large and dense proportion of the Muslim population of Nigeria.

But various photos and videos coming out of northern Nigeria from Nigerian Pentecostal and charismatic Christian missionaries and even Muslim background Pentecostal Christian missionaries in northern Nigeria show entire villages, converting to Christianity with small house churches being established all over the various villages of northern Nigeria.

For proof of the same, I shall be attaching below the photos and videos I have obtained from the public domain, while also attaching the links to the accounts from where these photos and videos have been obtained -

The above video shows a large number of Northern/Hausa-Fulani Muslims who have converted to Christianity and are now attending a local Pentecostal house church in their own village, for the source please refer to the following link

: <https://x.com/i/status/2035293315877249449>

The above video shows a Pentecostal church service attended by Fulani Christian converts as shown by a Fulani Ex-Muslim convert to Christianity from Nigeria serving as a frontline christian missionary to the muslims of northern Nigeria, for more information kindly refer to the following link : https://x.com/Preach_DGospel/status/1996951528301621558?s=20

The above video shows a conference for Fulani Christians in northern Nigeria as documented by a Fulani Ex-Muslim convert to Christianity from Nigeria serving as a frontline christian missionary to the muslims of northern Nigeria, for more information kindly refer to the following link
: https://x.com/Preach_DGospel/status/1896275628506378632?s=20

Photo of a frontline Christian missionary from a fulani muslim background in northern Nigeria preaching to Hausa muslims in northern Nigeria, for more information kindly refer to the following link : https://x.com/Preach_DGospel/status/2047023509012873501?s=20

However, even with all these photos and videos, if one were so inclined to refuse it, by saying that these converts are actually a small portion of the total Muslim population of Nigeria, what would be the best survey that could actually conclusively prove the mass conversion of Muslim to Christianity in Nigeria, and the fact that Nigeria is conclusively, actually a Christian majority country and no longer a Muslim majority country?

To answer this question, I shall present below a recent survey conducted by the PEW research organisation in the year 2025, regarding the attitude of people across various countries towards Israel and its prime minister, Benjamin Netanyahu as conclusive evidence of all my arguments of Nigeria actually being a Christian majority country given above.

THE PEW RESEARCH SURVEY :

Before we get to the facts about the survey and how it was conducted and also the results of the survey, it must be explained that the ordinary Pentecostal and charismatic Christian is extremely supportive of Israel, and also it's elected representatives and leaders, despite the circumstances or the opinion of the rest of the world as the theological [and ultimately the moral] framework of Pentecostal and Charismatic Christians explicitly endorses various pro-Judeo and pro-Israel teachings of the bible, including verses from the bible, such as Genesis 12:3, Numbers 24:9 and also Paul's earliest instructions issued to the church through his letters [which are now part of the bible] such as Romans 11:26.

It is therefore, due to this theological background that Pentecostal christians and leaders alike are extremely pro-Israel lobbying the governments of their respective countries [where they have reached a significant portion of the population] to take extremely pro-israeli stances even in light of the extremely unpopular Israeli war in Gaza that saw almost the entirety of the Gaza strip destroyed.

Now coming to the survey which was conducted in the year 2025 by the PEW Research organisation, it specifically was to find people's opinions on the war in Gaza between Israel and Hamas and also peoples support for the Israeli PM - Benjamin Netanyahu from as many 24 different countries [49] [50] [51].

In the said survey, respondents from the country of Nigeria showed the highest support for the Israeli PM Benjamin Netanyahu and they also the highest favourable opinion of the nation of Israel and its war in Gaza, with nearly 59% of the total number of respondents surveyed having a favourable opinion of the nation of Israel and its war in Gaza [52] [53] [54].

International views of Israel

In 20 of the 24 countries surveyed, around half of adults or more have an unfavorable view of Israel. Around three-quarters or more hold this view in Australia, Greece, Indonesia, Japan, the Netherlands, Spain, Sweden and Turkey.

Views of Israel are fairly divided in India (34% favorable, 29% unfavorable).

In Kenya and Nigeria, around half of adults or more have a favorable view of Israel.

How views have changed in recent years

The recent survey is not the first time Pew Research Center has asked about international

Most in surveyed nations have negative views of Israel

Note: Those who did not answer are not shown.
Source: Spring 2025 Global Attitudes Survey.
PEW RESEARCH CENTER

For more information kindly refer to the following link : <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/06/03/most-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu/>

Note that in the picture attached above the area highlighted in Red corresponds to the nation of Nigeria and its views on Israel and Blue highlighted text corresponds to the nation of Turkey and its views on Israel and the area highlighted in Green corresponds to the nation of Indonesia and its views on Israel following the Israel-Hamas war in the Gaza strip.

Notice that the countries of Indonesia and Turkey, which are both generally considered as moderate Muslim countries, where there is freedom of religion and secularism and multiculturalism have a majority of their population holding negative views regarding Israel with 80% of all Indonesians surveyed viewing Israel negatively and 93% of all Turkish citizens surveyed viewing Israel negatively [55]. Now compare that in sharp contrast with the nation of Nigeria, where nearly 59% of everyone surveyed viewed Israel positively, with barely 32% viewing Israel negatively [56].

This is not just an anomaly, but perhaps the greatest proof or evidence yet of Nigeria, being a Christian majority country in fact. Now the reason why I say this, is because Nigeria has one of the most radicalised muslim concentration and population in the whole world, where 12 out of 36 Nigerian states have adopted Sharia law, not just for personal law related matters like marriage, divorce and inheritance, but they have also extended Sharia law towards the criminal jurisdiction where Sharia law determines the penal code and the penalties for various crimes. Another aspect of this anomaly is also that Nigeria has one of the most concentrated and largest presence of Islamist terror groups such as the Boko Haram terror group, which began in the Maiduguri state of Nigeria [57] and the ISIS affiliated ISWAP terror group, which still operates in various parts of north and north eastern Nigeria [58]. Apart from this, Nigeria also ranks as the 7th most dangerous nation to be a Christian on the open doors watchlist [59] due to the pre-meditated and systematic form of attacks and killings of Christians over the last 10 years in Nigeria, where even the President of the United States of America i.e. Donald Trump has accused the government of Nigeria of committing a "christian genocide" in Nigeria [60].

Now, play the devil's advocate with me here for a minute - if the statistics given in the CIA Factbook in 2018 are true and every Christian person in Nigeria (of the 45% given in the CIA factbook) is in favour of Israel, that would still mean that 14% of the rest of the population which is 14% of the 53% of the population that is muslim, supports Israel and supports the Israeli genocide of fellow Palestinian Muslims residing in Gaza, which again roughly means that 26% of all Muslims living in Nigeria or rather 1 in every 4 Muslims in Nigeria support the Israelis and them genociding fellow Arab Muslims in Gaza (an impossible and unrealistic situation and statistic, when you take into consideration that just 7% of the Turkish population support Israel and only 20% of the Indonesian population support Israel **and both of these countries are moderate muslim countries in the terms that they follow the secular, moderate and liberal version of islam**).

Alternatively, if we were to assume that the statistics given by the PEW research group in 2019 were true [as given above], where it places the Muslim population at 50% of the total population of Nigeria and the Christian population at just 48%; then by extending this population estimate to the 2025 survey and assuming that every Christian [who makes up 48% of the total population of Nigeria according to the 2019 estimate of PEW research organisation] was in support of Israel's actions in Gaza, that would still mean that roughly 9-11% of the total population of Nigeria, who supported or had favourable views of Israel,

were muslims [who make up 50% of the total population of Nigeria, according to the 2019 estimate of PEW research organisation]. This would fairly imply **that roughly 9-11 out of every 50 Muslims in Nigeria or rather 18 to 22% of Nigeria's Muslim population was having favourable view of Israel or still supported Israel despite Israel actions during their war in Gaza** which is again an impossible and unrealistic scenario, when you take into consideration that just 7% of the Turkish population support Israel and only 20% of the Indonesian population support Israel and both of these countries are moderate muslim countries in the terms that they follow the secular, moderate and liberal version of islam.

Therefore the only other rational explanation that exists for 59% of all adults living in Nigeria supporting Israel and the Israeli genocide of Arab Muslims in Gaza, is that a majority of the population of Nigeria is actually Christian [with a clear majority of those Christians, being Christians belonging to the Pentecostal and Charismatic sect of Christianity]. And by majority of the population, I mean that anywhere between 52% to 56% of the population of Nigeria is actually Christian currently with only a small minority of Muslims, actually supporting Israel [give or take 3% of the total Nigerian population and 6% of the Nigerian Muslim population].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the explosive growth of Pentecostal and Charismatic Christianity in Nigeria represents one of the most remarkable spiritual shifts in modern history. What centuries of Islamic expansion through jihad, caliphates, and cultural dominance could not permanently secure is being steadily overturned, not by force of arms, but by the fervent preaching of the Gospel, mass crusades, and the bold witness of believers empowered by the Holy Spirit.

From the sweeping crusades of Reinhard Bonnke that ushered in tens of millions of conversions, to the grassroots expansion of house churches reaching deep into the Muslim north, Pentecostal Christians have taken the Great Commission seriously: preaching the Gospel to every creature and making disciples of all nations. The evidence is compelling, with shifting demographic surveys showing Christians now forming a clear majority, widespread conversions even among Hausa and Fulani communities, and Nigeria's strikingly pro-Israel stance in global opinion polls, which would be inconceivable in a Muslim-majority context.

Nigeria stands today as a powerful case study in de-Islamisation through spiritual awakening. What began as a bold counter to centuries of gradual Islamisation has produced a vibrant, growing Christian majority that is reshaping the spiritual, cultural, and even geopolitical landscape of Africa's most populous nation.

As Nigeria continues on this trajectory, it offers hope and a model for other nations facing similar pressures: that the power of the Holy Spirit working through zealous, obedient

believers can reverse even deeply entrenched spiritual strongholds. The Church in Nigeria must remain faithful to its evangelistic calling, guarding this divine momentum with prayer, integrity, and continued boldness. What God has begun in this land, He is well able to complete, for His glory and the advancement of His Kingdom.

The transformation of Nigeria stands as a testimony that no ideology, no matter how aggressive or long-established, can ultimately withstand the advancing tide of the Gospel when God's people rise up in faith and obedience.

CITATIONS :

1. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/islamization>
2. <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/from-the-struggle-for-independence-to-the-religious-conflict/92615#:~:text=What%20is%20Islamization>
3. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/islamization>
4. <https://worldwithoutgenocide.org/genocides-and-conflicts/the-ottoman-christian-genocide#:~:text=While%20Armenians%20were%20the%20most%20affluent%20and%20widely%20persecuted%20group%2C%20perpetrators%20sought%20to%20purge%20the%20Ottoman%20Empire%20of%20all%20Christian%20minorities.%20This%20included%20Assyrians%20and%20Greeks.%20Scholars%20estimate%20that%201.5%20million%20Armenians%20were%20slaughtered%2C%20but%20the%20total%20death%20toll%20is%20over%202%20million%20people.%C2%A0>
5. <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/coptic/coptic.html#:~:text=according%20to%20the%20geographer%20Al%2DMuqaddasi%2C%20Copts%20were%20still%20in%20the%20majority%20in%20the%2010th%20century%2C%20almost%20four%20centuries%20after%20the%20Moslem%20annexation%20of%20Egypt>
6. [https://grokipedia.com/page/Christianity_in_Egypt#ref-56:~:text=Prior%20to%20the%20Arab%20conquest%20\(639,preserving%20elements%20of%20Egyptian%20cultural%20legacy.](https://grokipedia.com/page/Christianity_in_Egypt#ref-56:~:text=Prior%20to%20the%20Arab%20conquest%20(639,preserving%20elements%20of%20Egyptian%20cultural%20legacy.)
- 6(a). https://www.copticchurch.net/pdf/intro/arab_conquest_of_egypt.pdf
7. <https://www.thoughtco.com/early-christianity-in-north-africa-part-1-44461#:~:text=Given%20the%20slow%20progress%20of%20Romanization%20of%20North%20Africa%2C%20it%20is%20perhaps%20surprising%20how%20quickly%20Christianity%20spread%20across%20the%20top%20of%20the%20continent>

17. <https://www.britannica.com/place/western-Africa/The-jihad-of-USman-dan-Fodio#:~:text=The%20jihad%20of%20Usman%20dan%20Fodio>
18. <https://historicalnigeria.com/the-jihad-of-usman-dan-fodio-and-the-rise-of-the-sokoto-caliphate/#:~:text=By%201808%2C%20the,and%20religious%20accountability>
19. <https://africanhistory.online/history?id=1746521873#:~:text=The%20caliphate%E2%80%99s%20territory%20eventually%20spanned%20over%201%20million%20square%20kilometers>
20. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326509602_BRITISH_INDIRECT_RULE_AND_ISLAM_IN_NORTHERN_NIGERIA_1900-1940
21. <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/wp-content/uploads/sites/7/2011/12/Christianity-fullreport-web.pdf>
- 21(a). <https://web.archive.org/web/20260531102209/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.pewresearch.org%2Freligion%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2Fsites%2F7%2F2011%2F12%2FChristianity-fullreport-web.pdf>
22. <https://joynews.co.za/africa-shall-be-saved-cfan-celebrates-50-years-of-sharing-the-gospel/#:~:text=They%20have%20never%20looked%20back%20since%2C%20growing%20from%20strength%20to%20strength%20and%20witnessing%20moments%20like%20a%20million%20people%20attending%20a%20single%20service%20in%20Lagos%20in%202000>
- 22(a). <https://web.archive.org/web/20260531102547/https%3A%2F%2Fjoynews.co.za%2Fafrica-shall-be-saved-cfan-celebrates-50-years-of-sharing-the-gospel%2F#:~:text=They%20have%20never%20looked%20back%20since%2C%20growing%20from%20strength%20to%20strength%20and%20witnessing%20moments%20like%20a%20million%20people%20attending%20a%20single%20service%20in%20Lagos%20in%202000>
23. <https://thejesusculture.org/reinhard-bonnke-nigeria-1999-over-15-million-decisions-for-jesus-christ/>
- 23(a). <https://web.archive.org/web/20260531102651/https%3A%2F%2Fthejesusculture.org%2Freinhard-bonnke-nigeria-1999-over-15-million-decisions-for-jesus-christ%2F>

24.

https://www.cfan.eu/fileadmin/bilder/press_material/History_of_Christ_for_all_Nations.pdf

25. Refer to Chapter 16 and page 170 of the book bearing ISBN Number : 9780857210456 & 9781854249814

26. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/20566093.2016.1085240#d1e286>

27.

[https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/20566093.2016.1085240#d1e286:~:text=m any%20of%20which%2C%20presumably%2C%20have%20been%20established%20to%20pr ovide%20the%20kind%20of%20organizational%20equivalent%20that%20would%20stop%2 0the%20hemorrhaging%20of%20young%20Muslim%20men%20and%20women%20to%20P entecostal%20groups](https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/20566093.2016.1085240#d1e286:~:text=m%20any%20of%20which%2C%20presumably%2C%20have%20been%20established%20to%20pr%20vide%20the%20kind%20of%20organizational%20equivalent%20that%20would%20stop%20the%20hemorrhaging%20of%20young%20Muslim%20men%20and%20women%20to%20P%20entecostal%20groups)

28.

[https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/hemorrhage#:~:text=to%20lose%20a% 20large%20amount%20of%20blood%20in%20a%20short%20time%3A](https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/hemorrhage#:~:text=to%20lose%20a%20large%20amount%20of%20blood%20in%20a%20short%20time%3A)

29. <https://www.merriam->

[webster.com/dictionary/hemorrhage#:~:text=to%20lose%20rapidly%20and%20uncontrolla bly](https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/hemorrhage#:~:text=to%20lose%20rapidly%20and%20uncontrolla bly)

30. [https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2019/04/01/the-countries-with-the-10- largest-christian-populations-and-the-10-largest-muslim-populations/ft_19-03-](https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2019/04/01/the-countries-with-the-10-largest-christian-populations-and-the-10-largest-muslim-populations/ft_19-03-29_muslimchristianpopulations_muslim-)

[29_muslimchristianpopulations_muslim-](https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2019/04/01/the-countries-with-the-10-largest-christian-populations-and-the-10-largest-muslim-populations/ft_19-03-29_muslimchristianpopulations_muslim-)

[png/#:~:text=LARGEST%20MUSLIM%20POPULATIONS,-10%20countries%20with%20the%2 0largest%20Muslim%20populations%2C%202015%20and%202060,-DOWNLOAD](https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2019/04/01/the-countries-with-the-10-largest-christian-populations-and-the-10-largest-muslim-populations/ft_19-03-29_muslimchristianpopulations_muslim-png/#:~:text=LARGEST%20MUSLIM%20POPULATIONS,-10%20countries%20with%20the%2 0largest%20Muslim%20populations%2C%202015%20and%202060,-DOWNLOAD)

31. <https://web.archive.org/web/20210109223449/https://www.cia.gov/the-world->

[factbook/countries/nigeria/#:~:text=Muslim%2053.5%25%2C%20Roman%20Catholic%201 0.6%25%2C%20other%20Christian%2035.3%25%2C%20other%20.6%25%20\(2018%20est](https://web.archive.org/web/20210109223449/https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/nigeria/#:~:text=Muslim%2053.5%25%2C%20Roman%20Catholic%201 0.6%25%2C%20other%20Christian%2035.3%25%2C%20other%20.6%25%20(2018%20est)

32. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/11/11/5-facts-about-religion-in->

[nigeria/#:~:text=As%20of%202020%2C%20Muslims%20made%20up%20a%20majority%20 of%20Nigeria%E2%80%99s%20total%20population%20\(56.1%25\)%2C%20while%20Christia ns%20made%20up%2043.4%25%2C%20according%20to%20our%20estimates](https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/11/11/5-facts-about-religion-in-nigeria/#:~:text=As%20of%202020%2C%20Muslims%20made%20up%20a%20majority%20 of%20Nigeria%E2%80%99s%20total%20population%20(56.1%25)%2C%20while%20Christia ns%20made%20up%2043.4%25%2C%20according%20to%20our%20estimates)

32(a).

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260602132347/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.pewresearch.org%2 Fshort-reads%2F2025%2F11%2F11%2F5-facts-about-religion-in- nigeria%2F#:~:text=As%20of%202020%2C%20Muslims%20made%20up%20a%20majority>

%20of%20Nigeria%E2%80%99s%20total%20population%20(56.1%25)%2C%20while%20Christians%20made%20up%2043.4%25%2C%20according%20to%20our%20estimates

33. https://web.archive.org/web/20210126035703/https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2019/04/01/the-countries-with-the-10-largest-christian-populations-and-the-10-largest-muslim-populations/ft_19-03-29_muslimchristianpopulations_christian/

34. https://web.archive.org/web/20210130095538/https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2019/04/01/the-countries-with-the-10-largest-christian-populations-and-the-10-largest-muslim-populations/ft_19-03-29_muslimchristianpopulations_muslim/

35. <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR395/FR395.pdf>

35(a).

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260604153208/https%3A%2F%2Fdhsprogram.com%2Fpubs%2Fpdf%2FFR395%2FFR395.pdf>

36. <https://citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/>

37. Refer to Page 4 of the following link :

https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/DEMOGRAPHIC_BULLETIN_2022_FINAL.pdf

38. <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/>

39. <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/largest-ethnic-groups-in-nigeria.html#:~:text=The%20Hausa%20are%20the%20biggest%20ethnic%20group%20in%20Nigeria.%20With%20estimates%20of%20their%20population%20reaching%2067%20million%2C%20Hausa%20make%20up%20approximately%2025%25%20of%20the%20Nigerian%20population>

40. <https://guardian.ng/nigerian/what-are-the-three-ethnic-groups-in-nigeria/#:~:text=The%20Hausa%2DFulani%20people%20represent%20approximately%2029%25%20of%20Nigeria%E2%80%99s%20population%2C%20making%20them%20our%20numerically%20largest%20ethnic%20group>

41. <https://guardian.ng/nigerian/what-are-the-three-ethnic-groups-in-nigeria/#:~:text=The%20Yoruba%20people%2C%20constituting%20roughly%2021%25%20of%20Nigeria%E2%80%99s%20population%2C%20dominate%20the%20southwestern%20states%20of%20Lagos%2C%20Ogun%2C%20Oyo%2C%20Osun%2C%20Ondo%2C%20and%20Ekiti>

42. Refer to Page 4 of the following link :

https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/DEMOGRAPHIC_BULLETIN_2022_FINAL.pdf

43.

<https://www.refworld.org/reference/countryrep/mrgi/2018/en/120270#:~:text=Igbo%20make%20up%20around%2018%20per%20cent%20of%20Nigeria%27s%20population.%20Thei%20traditional%20homeland%20straddles%20the%20Niger%20River%20in%20the%20south%20Deast%20and%20is%20one%20of%20the%20most%20densely%20populated%20areas%20of%20the%20African%20continent.%20Igbo%20are%20predominantly%20Christian>

44. <https://www.afrobarometer.org/publication/nigeria-round-10-summary-of-results/>

44(a).

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260602133056/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.afrobarometer.org%2Fpublication%2Fnigeria-round-10-summary-of-results%2F>

45. <https://www.afrobarometer.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/R10-Summary-of-results-Nigeria-Afrobarometer-bh-7aug25-rev-1nov25.pdf>

45(a).

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260602132723/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.afrobarometer.org%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2025%2F08%2FR10-Summary-of-results-Nigeria-Afrobarometer-bh-7aug25-rev-1nov25.pdf>

46. <https://www.afrobarometer.org/publication/nigeria-round-9-summary-of-results/>

46(a).

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260602133429/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.afrobarometer.org%2Fpublication%2Fnigeria-round-9-summary-of-results%2F>

47. <https://www.afrobarometer.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Nigeria-Afrobarometer-R9-Summary-of-Results-26august2022.pdf>

47(a). <https://web.archive.org/web/20260304153658/https://www.afrobarometer.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Nigeria-Afrobarometer-R9-Summary-of-Results-26august2022.pdf>

48. https://www.afrobarometer.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/ab_r7_dispatchno339_pap12_religion_in_africa.pdf

48(a). https://web.archive.org/web/20260220104619/https://www.afrobarometer.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/ab_r7_dispatchno339_pap12_religion_in_africa.pdf

49. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/06/03/most-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu/>

50.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260527201837/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.pewresearch.org%2Fshort-reads%2F2025%2F06%2F03%2Fmost-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu%2F>

51. <https://perma.cc/D6TQ-95WK>

52. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/06/03/most-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu/#:~:text=In%20Kenya%20and%20Nigeria%2C%20around%20half%20of%20adults%20or%20more%20have%20a%20favorable%20view%20of%20Israel>

53.

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260527201837/https%3A%2F%2Fwww.pewresearch.org%2Fshort-reads%2F2025%2F06%2F03%2Fmost-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu%2F#:~:text=In%20Kenya%20and%20Nigeria%2C%20around%20half%20of%20adults%20or%20more%20have%20a%20favorable%20view%20of%20Israel>

54. <https://perma.cc/D6TQ-95WK>

55. https://web.archive.org/web/20260405092119/https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/06/03/most-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu/sr_25-06-03_views-of-israel_1/

56. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2025/06/03/most-people-across-24-surveyed-countries-have-negative-views-of-israel-and-netanyahu/#:~:text=Kenya%20and%20Nigeria%2C%20around%20half%20of%20adults%20or%20more%20have%20a%20favorable%20view%20of%20Israel>

57. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-13809501>

58. https://www.dni.gov/nctc/terrorist_groups/isis_west_africa.html

59. <https://www.opendoors.org/en-US/persecution/countries/>

60. <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/11/21/world/africa/nigeria-trump-genocide-claims.html>

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